

ALUMINUM/ CUBIC BORON NITRIDE FUNCTIONALLY GRADED GRINDING WHEEL FOR DRILLING CFRP FABRICATED BY THE CENTRIFUGAL MIXED-POWDER METHOD

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ABSTRACT

Making holes is the most common postprocessing operation performed on CFRP for producing riveted and bolted joints during assembly operations. In fact, there are more than a million drilled holes in modern commercial aircraft. Recently, a novel machining technology, i.e., the gyro-driving grinding wheel system has been developed for machining CFRP. This system provides large holes on CFRP without burr and delamination. However, resin-bonded grinding wheels or vitreous bond grinding wheels are not necessarily very suitable. This is because when the grinding wheel is used for the gyro-driving grinding wheel system, it is subjected to the torsion force. With the above in mind, we are developing metal / diamond functionally graded grinding wheel by the centrifugal mixed-powder method. As first step of this process, powder mixture of diamond particles and metal particles is inserted into spinning mold. After that, molten metal matrix is poured into the spinning mold with powder mixture. As a result, the molten metal matrix penetrates into the space between the particles by the pressure due to the centrifugal force. At the same time, metal particles are melted by matrix melt poured from crucible. Finally, a functionally graded grinding wheel can be obtained. Meanwhile, cubic boron nitride (cBN) is the second hardest material after synthetic diamond. In this study, as an attempt to improve the tool life of grinding wheels, aluminium / cBN functionally graded grinding wheels for the gyro-driving grinding wheel system have been fabricated by the centrifugal mixed-powder method. Grinding ability of the fabricated functionally graded grinding wheels has been evaluated by wear tests.

1 INTRODUCTION

The demand for higher productivity and lower manufacturing costs has imposed a need for the development of cutting tools capable of operating at high cutting speeds. High machining speeds generate higher stresses and increase the temperature at the tool-workpiece interface and require better refractory tool materials. A cutting tool for difficult-to-cut materials expected to perform under severe machining condition should have adequate fracture toughness, high hot hardness, thermal shock resistance, and must be chemically stable and inert at the operating temperatures [1].

Meanwhile, carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) is a very strong and light composite material. Due to its high ratio of strength to weight, it has many applications in aerospace and automotive fields. CFRP parts are manufactured near-net shape, however, additional machining operations such as drilling and milling may be required to meet final design specifications [2]. There are typical problems encountered when drilling CFRP. These problems include the delamination of the composites, rapid tool wear, fiber pullout, presence of powdery chip, etc. [3-5].

Takekoshi *et al.* have been developing the high-precision drilling technology for CFRP by using a gyro-driving grinding wheel system with dual-axis-driven mechanism [6-9]. A schematic illustration of the gyro-driving grinding wheel system with dual-axis-driven mechanism is shown in Fig.1 [7-11]. In the gyro-driving grinding wheel system, a grinding wheel was used instead of drill bits for drilling. Since this system has dual-spin axes, one is the grinding wheel axis and the other is tool axis, moving locust of abrasive grain becomes sphere. This situation results in the making a circular hole on the CFRP.

Figure 1: Schematic illustration of the gyro-driving grinding wheel system with dual-axis-driven mechanism [7-11].

Grinding wheels are composed of selectively sized abrasive grains held together by a bonding material. Standard grinding wheel bonds are vitrified, silicate, resinoid, rubber, shellac, oxychloride and metal. However, resin-bonded grinding wheels and vitreous bond grinding wheels are not necessarily very suitable for the equipment for the gyro-driving grinding wheel system. This is because the grinding wheel is subjected the torsion force, as shown in Fig. 1. This situation is more severe when the size of holes becomes smaller and thickness of the grinding wheel has to become thinner. Candidate grinding wheels applicable for the gyro-driving grinding wheel system are, therefore, metal-bonded grinding wheels. Traditional metal-bonded grinding wheels are fabricated by connection of segments consist of small-size abrasive particles and metal bond materials with the metallic bodies of the grinding wheel tools. However, the junction of them will tend to break because of the uneven heat and forces received by the two layers. This shortcoming can be overcome by using the concept of functionally graded materials (FGMs) [10-12].

Watanabe *et al.* [10-13] are proposing a centrifugal mixed-powder method as a novel processing technique to fabricate FGMs. The experimental procedure of the centrifugal mixed-powder method is summarized in Fig. 2 [10, 11, 13]. As a first step, a powder mixture of abrasive grains and metal matrix particles is inserted into a spinning mold (Fig. 2 (a)). After that, the molten metal matrix is poured into the spinning mold with the powder mixture (Fig. 2 (b)). As a result, the molten metal matrix penetrates into the space between the particles due to the pressure exerted by the centrifugal force (Fig. 2 (c)). At the same time, the metal matrix powder is melted by the heat from poured molten matrix (Fig. 2(d)). Finally, ring shaped FGMs with abrasive grains distributed on its surface can be obtained (Fig. 2 (e)).

Figure 2: Schematic illustration showing the process of the centrifugal mixed-powder method [10, 11, 13].

In our previous studies, diamond particles are used as abrasive grains [12, 14]. Alternatively, in this study, cubic boron nitride (cBN) will be used, since it is the second hardest material next to the diamond and possess many excellent physical, chemical and mechanical properties such as a thermal stability up to 1200°C, high resistance to chemical attack, high hardness (~6000 HV) and Young modulus (~900 GPa) values [15-17]. Basic properties and characteristics of cBN and other hard materials used as abrasive listed in Table 1 [16]. As can be seen, the properties of cBN are relatively close to those of diamond.

Materials	cBN	Diamond	WC	SiC
Density [Mg/m ³]	3.45	3.51	14.7	3.20
Knoop Hardness [GPa]	45	57-104	13	32
Compressive Strength [GPa]	5.33	8.68	4.5	3.9
Thermal Conductivity [W/mK]	740	600-2000	100	120
Thermal Expansion (10 ⁻⁶ °C ⁻¹)	1.2	1.5-4.8	5.4	4.0

Table 1: Properties of abrasive materials [16].

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Pure Al particles of 99.9% purity having sizes in the range of 75 - 150 µm and abrasive grains (cBN particles or diamond particles) having sizes in the range of 125 - 150 µm were used as primary materials. The volume fraction of abrasive grains in the powder mixture was 25 vol.%. The prepared mixed-powder was set in a compact vacuum centrifugal caster, shown in Fig. 3. For ideal processing, the centrifugal direction in centrifugal casting should correspond to the radial direction of the ring, sintering as shown in Fig. 2. However, this vacuum centrifugal casting machine was used due to a convenient means for experiment because of machine performance [12]. The mold was prepared by a lost-wax process, and the sample size was approximately φ 20 mm x 39 mm excluding sprue and runner. The hollow section of the cast was made by use of core, as also shown in Fig. 3.

The pure Al of 99.99% purity (30g) was placed in the melting crucible surrounded by the induction coil. After the Al melt reached to the desired temperature, the mold and the crucible were rotated for 99 s and the molten Al was poured into the mold cavity, where applied centrifugal force was 80 G. It is well known that addition of Al-Ti-X alloys (X=B or C) containing potent nucleant particles, such as

Al_3Ti and TiB_2 or TiC , is the most popular method for refining the grain structure of Al alloys during the solidification processes [18-21]. It is expected that the grain structure of Al matrix in FGMs fabricated by the centrifugal mixed-powder method with Al_3Ti or Ti particles becomes more refined than that fabricated without Al_3Ti or Ti particles, results in the better mechanical properties [22, 23]. Therefore, in this study, Al_3Ti or Ti particles were also mixed into the mixed-powder. Table 2 summarizes the casting conditions with mixed-powder.

Figure 3: Schematic illustration of compact vacuum centrifugal caster used in this study.

Sample	Al-cBN	Al-4% Al_3Ti - cBN	Al-6% Al_3Ti - cBN	Al-8% Al_3Ti - cBN	Al-4% Ti- cBN	Al- Diamond
Amount of abrasive grains [g]	cBN 1.19	cBN 1.19	cBN 1.19	cBN 1.19	cBN 1.19	Diamond 1.17
Amount of Al particles [g]	2.73	2.64	2.60	2.55	2.66	2.73
Amount of Al_3Ti particles [g]	-	0.11 (4mass%)	0.17 (6mass%)	0.22 (8mass%)	-	-
Amount of Ti particles [g]	-	-	-	-	0.11 (4mass%)	-
Casting Temperature [°C]	1350	1350	1350	1350	1400	1350

Table 2: Casting conditions.

The microstructural observations of the fabricated samples were carried out with an optical microscope (OM) and scanning electron microscope (SEM: JSM-5900LV, JEOL, Japan) after the polishing. Composition of each of the samples was identified by SEM with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS: JED-2200).

After the polishing, the samples for bonding force test were deeply etched by 10% hydrofluoric acid for 200 sec to 250 sec. This selective etching results in the exposure of the abrasive grains from Al matrix. The bonding force between abrasive grains (cBN particles or diamond particles) and the Al matrix was tested at room temperature using a bonding force measurement system (RHESCA, PTR-1101, Japan). Figure 4 is schematic illustration of the bonding force test, where the shear height was fixed to be 15 μm , in this study. The probe with a mechanical sensor was set at an appropriate position by the controller. Then the probe moved horizontally at 100 $\mu\text{m}/\text{s}$ and pushed the abrasive grains, where the shear force was recorded by the mechanical sensor. In the bonding force test, 50 abrasive grains in each sample were picked to be sheared.

Figure 4: Schematic illustration of bonding force test.

A brock-shaped sample with 3.5mm x 3.5mm x 15mm in size was cut for wear test. The counterpart was a disc with 80 mm in diameter, and was made from alloy tool steel (SKD11, HV=217). The surface of the counter disc was polished with no. 800 emery paper. Wear tests were performed using a brock-on-disc wear machine (RHESCA, FPR-2100, Japan) under rotating movement. The sliding velocity, load and duration in the wear tests were 0.46 m/s, 500 g and 7.2 ksec, respectively. After the wear tests, weight loss of the samples was measured. Moreover, the depth of the wear groove for the counter disc was measured by digital microscope (KEYENCE, VHX-1000, Japan) to evaluate material removal performance. Grinding ratio R , defined as the volume of material removed per unit volume of sample wear, is then calculated.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figures 5 (a) and (b) show the OM and SEM secondary electron images of Al-cBN sample, respectively. As can be seen from these figures, Al particles in the mixed-powder were fully melted by heat from molten Al. Subsequently, the cBN abrasive grains were successfully embedded in the Al matrix. The OM image shown in Fig. 5 (a) reveals that homogeneous distribution of cBN abrasive grains takes place in the Al matrix. The uniform distribution of cBN abrasive grains is influenced by good interfacial bonding of cBN abrasive grains with Al matrix. SEM image shown in Fig. 5 (b) reveals angular edges of cBN particles and a clear interface between Al matrix and cBN particle. It is reported cBN-particle-dispersed Al matrix composites could be fabricated in solid-liquid co-existent state by spark plasma sintering (SPS) process from the mixture of cBN powders, Al powders and Al-5 mass% Si powders. During SPS process, no reaction at the interface between the cBN particle and the Al matrix was observed for the composites fabricated at a temperature range between 525 °C and 603 °C for 26 min [24]. Moreover, it is reported that no transformation of cBN to hBN was detected in the Al₂O₃-cBN composites containing 20 vol% cBN fabricated by SPS at 1300 °C for 600 s [25]. Therefore, the absence of a chemical reaction of cBN with the Al matrix and transformation of cBN is also expected in our sample. The interface between the matrix and the reinforcement plays an important role in determination of the properties of the metal matrix composites, since the interface acts as a bridge for load transfer from the matrix to the reinforcement. It is important to eliminate the formation of a brittle layer at the matrix/reinforcement interface. The brittle layer at the interface is usually formed by the oxidation of the reinforcements or by reactions between matrix and reinforcement during the fabrication steps or under high temperature service conditions [26]. The absence of the formation of a brittle layer at the matrix/reinforcement interface offers a strong capability of this system to use as grinding wheel in CFRP drilling application.

OM and SEM secondary electron images of Al-diamond sample are shown in Figs. 6 (a) and (b), respectively. Again, the diamond abrasive grains are successfully embedded in the Al matrix. The homogeneous distribution of diamond abrasive grains in the sample could be found, as shown in Fig. 6 (a). Although wettability between Al and diamond is intrinsically good, some gaps were observed

between Al particles and Al matrix, as shown in Fig. 6 (b). Since such gaps cannot be observed in Al-cBN sample, better bonding force between the abrasive grains and the Al matrix is expected for the Al-cBN sample.

Figure 5: (a) OM and (b) SEM images of the Al-cBN sample.

Figure 6: (a) OM and (b) SEM images of the Al-diamond sample.

To study the bonding force between the abrasive grains and the Al matrix, bonding tests were carried out. When the bonding tests are performed, fracture or delamination of the abrasive grains was occurred. Figure 7 is a set of schematic illustrations showing the fracture and the detachment types of the abrasive grains by the bonding tests. In addition, typical force-displacement curves for each behavior type are presented in Fig. 8. By the bonding tests, three kinds of the fracture and the detachment-types are mainly observed, as shown in Fig. 7. When the probe touches the abrasive grain and started to push it, Al matrix is shear deformed without the fracture and the detachment of the abrasive grain. This behavior is defined as type A, as shown in Fig. 7 (a). As the result, the force-displacement curve of type A is similar with typical load-displacement curves of metallic materials, as shown in Fig. 8 (a). On the other hand, when the bonding tests are carried out, the abrasive grains are sometimes fragmented by shear deformation. This fracture behavior is denoted as type B, as shown in Fig. 7 (b). In case of type B, the force is dropped down without plastic deformation, since brittle fracture of the abrasive grain is occurred, as shown in Fig. 8 (b). Finally, the behavior of type C is the detachment of the abrasive grain from the matrix, as shown in Fig. 7 (c). When the shear stress is induced to the abrasive grain, the abrasive grain is detached and pulled out from the matrix. Because of this, as shown in Fig. 8 (c), the force during the bonding test under type C is increased until detachment of the abrasive grain, and subsequently decreased after the detachment. Considering about the bonding force between the abrasive grain and the matrix, the shear behavior of type A presents the highest bonding force among type A, type B and type C. In this study, results of the bonding tests for the Al-cBN sample and Al-Diamond sample were separated into these three types behavior based on microstructural change and the force-displacement diagram.

Figure 7: Definitions of type A, type B and type C fractures in bonding force test.

Figure 8: Typical displacement-force curves during bonding force test.

Figures 9(a) and (b) show appearance frequencies of type A, type B and type C by bonding tests for Al-cBN and Al-Diamond samples, respectively. As shown in Fig. 9 (a), in the Al-cBN sample, shear behavior of type A is occurred most frequently while fracture under type C is not observed. In case of the Al-Diamond samples, all of shear behavior types occur with similar frequency, although occurrence frequency of type A is the highest among three types. Comparing the bonding force of Al-cBN sample with that of Al-Diamond sample, the bonding force of the Al-cBN sample is higher. This means that the Al matrix has better bonding force with the cBN grain rather than the diamond grain. This would come from difference of wettability between the abrasive grain and the matrix. Hence, it can be expected that Al-cBN sample has better drilling ability as functionally graded grinding wheel comparing with Al-Diamond sample.

Figure 9: Appearance frequency of type A, type B and type C by bonding tests for (a) Al-cBN and (b) Al-Diamond samples.

Figure 10 shows the effect of Al_3Ti and Ti particles in the mixed-powder on microstructure. Higher magnification photographs with EDS analysis results for Al-6% Al_3Ti -cBN and Al-4% Ti-cBN samples are shown in Fig. 11. It is seen that Al_3Ti or Ti particles, as well as cBN particles, are homogeneously embedded in Al matrix. Moreover, Ti particle in Al-4% Ti-cBN is covered by Al_3Ti phase formed by the reaction of $3\text{Al} + \text{Ti} \rightarrow \text{Al}_3\text{Ti}$, as shown in Fig. 11 (b). Since Al_3Ti phase acts as a good nucleation site for Al matrix, it is expected that the grain structure of Al matrix in Al- Al_3Ti -cBN samples and Al-4% Ti-cBN sample is more refined than that of Al-cBN sample. Moreover, Al alloys reinforced with Al_3Ti possess high specific strength, high specific modulus, and excellent properties both at ambient and elevated temperature [26-28]. It is known that the presence of Al_3Ti phase is very effective in increasing the stiffness of Al alloys. Therefore, better mechanical properties could be achieved for Al- Al_3Ti -cBN samples and Al-4% Ti-cBN sample.

Figure 10: SEM images of (a) Al-4% Al_3Ti -cBN, (b) Al-6% Al_3Ti -cBN, (c) Al-8% Al_3Ti -cBN and (d) Al-4% Ti-cBN samples.

Figure 11: Higher magnification photographs with EDS analysis results for (a) Al-6%Al₃Ti-cBN and (b) Al-4%Ti-cBN samples.

Results of wear tests of the both functionally graded grinding wheel samples and counter disc specimens are shown in Fig. 12. As can be seen in Fig. 12, the weight loss of the Al-Al₃Ti-cBN samples and Al-4%Ti-cBN sample was much smaller than that of the Al-cBN sample, although smaller wear in the counter disc, i.e., smaller grinding performance, was found for the Al-Al₃Ti-cBN samples and Al-4%Ti-cBN sample.

To discuss the above, grinding ratio value of each sample was calculated and results are shown in Fig. 12. It is seen from this figure that the grinding ratio increases with increasing the amount of Al₃Ti particles in the mixed-powder, since the Al-4mass%Al₃Ti, Al-6mass%Al₃Ti and Al-8mass%Al₃Ti alloys correspond to Al-3.2vol%Al₃Ti, Al-4.9vol%Al₃Ti and Al-6.5vol%Al₃Ti alloys, respectively, and the volume fraction of Al₃Ti in the Al-4mass%Ti alloy is 8.8vol%, if 100% of Ti particles reacted into Al₃Ti phase. In this way, the addition of the Al₃Ti or Ti particles can increase the grinding ratio and improve the grinding performance, due to the grain refining effects in Al matrix and reinforced effects by Al₃Ti phase. The grinding ratio increases with less grinding wheel wear and/or higher CFRP removal. The higher it is, the better the grinding conditions, especially in terms of longer grinding wheel life.

Figure 12: Results of wear tests for Al-cBN, Al-4%Al₃Ti-cBN, Al-6%Al₃Ti-cBN, Al-8%Al₃Ti-cBN and Al-4%Ti-cBN samples.

Figure 13: Grinding ratio for Al-cBN, Al-4% Al₃Ti-cBN, Al-6% Al₃Ti-cBN, Al-8% Al₃Ti-cBN and Al-4% Ti-cBN samples.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, as an attempt to improve the tool life of grinding wheels, Al matrix cubic boron nitride (cBN) particles dispersed functionally graded grinding wheels, as well as diamond particles dispersed one, for the gyro-driving grinding wheel system have been fabricated by the centrifugal mixed-powder method. Influences of addition of Al₃Ti or Ti particles on the wear behavior are also investigated. From obtained results, it is found that the cBN particles have better bonding force between the abrasive grains and the Al matrix comparing with the diamond particles. Moreover, addition of the Al₃Ti or Ti particles can increase the grinding ratio and improve the grinding performance. Such Al-based functionally graded grinding wheels with high wear grinding performance would be suitable for the gyro-driving grinding wheel system with dual-axis-driven mechanism.

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